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Another Brick in the Wall?

Comment on “A systematic framework of creative metacognition”

by I. Lebuda & M. Benedek

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Creativity requires deliberate effort, some “thought control” to echo one of the greatest Pink Floyd pieces. Notably, however, this “control” comes in a constructive sense here. The framework Lebuda and Benedek offer, provides an inspiring perspective to study controllable mechanisms in creative ideation. This commentary discusses what the proposed framework actually frames. We also suggest directions that could enhance the model’s contribution and methodological challenges of its applications.

By mapping the foundational triad of *metacognitive knowledge, monitoring, and control* to the creativity context, Lebuda and Benedek integrated and applied the established theories of metacognition to the context of creative thinking. As they explain, there is nothing particularly creative about metacognition *per se*. While specific nuances or subcomponents of metacognition might emerge in creative contexts, the key premise of the model presented, i.e., the distinction into three interacting components, is broadly applicable to creative and non-creative tasks. Thus, the value of the proposed conceptualization does not lie in identifying novel metacognitive foundations specific to creative cognition but in overviewing functions or manifestations of these structures in creative ideation.

The model appears to be both broad and specialized simultaneously. This specialization is evident in the framework’s emphasis on the creative process observed during divergent thinking. Within this context, the mechanics of the model are clearly exemplified. Such a focus holds promise for synthesizing studies that reinterpret divergent thinking tasks as executive tasks [1] and, therefore, delve into people’s performance by identifying strategies they employ [2], actively inducing these strategies [3], examining the accuracy of people’s metacognitive monitoring [4], and providing metacognitive feedback [5], to name a few. This line of research could be further enriched by

incorporating the model's assumptions, for instance, by emphasizing dynamic, temporal patterns in creative metacognition.

However, it is less clear how this dynamic should be operationalized. Micro-longitudinal approaches [6] seem well-fitted to test within-person processes over time. Yet, examining shifts between stages, components, and levels appears challenging, requiring time-situated, densely temporal measures [7] and blended, multi-method approaches [8]. For example, metacognitive monitoring is assumed to inform metacognitive control regarding whether to engage in the task or allocate further resources for preparations. To truly understand this process—not merely record the output—one might need a fusion of different research tools: eye-tracking can shed light on attention shifts; reaction time can hint at the speed of decision-making; physiological measures can indicate arousal; and observational input can provide contextual cues. Yet simpler methods might also be fruitful. Elsewhere [9], Lebeda and Benedek operationalized the effectiveness of metacognitive control as a within-subject standardized difference in scores obtained in “be creative” versus “be fluent” conditions, thus capturing one's effort to adapt to the task instruction. Still, relying primarily on indirect measures or static, subjective assessments may be insufficient for testing the model's nuanced hypotheses. Focusing on refining current and generating new measures appears necessary to obtain fresh insights into how people monitor and control their task performance.

At the same time, the inherent “task-ness” of the framework poses challenges in applying it to other forms of creativity, those that go beyond divergent thinking. How do the elements of the model work in the case of composing a musical piece or designing new furniture? Or consider writing a novel: what constitutes “local,” response-level and “global,” task-level metacognitive processes? One writer might segment their work into portions like “developing main characters' profiles,” “world-building,” and “crafting plot twists,” while another, less experienced, might think about “writing the first chapter,” “writing the second chapter,” etc. (this task segmentation itself may be a product of metacognition). Are these all, in their own right, individual tasks, each with its own set of metacognitive activities? If we only consider “writing a novel” as the sole global task, we risk

trivializing the micro-level metacognitive processes that each “subtask” demands. In short, the three-tiered granularity might work well with divergent thinking task procedures yet it is harder to implement in real-life settings. Yet, while challenging, such a transition is needed if what is presented can work as a general framework of creative metacognition.

Moreover, creative actions are rarely initiated with explicit instructions, even as simple as a hint to “be creative.” People engage in everyday creative activities to have fun, cope with stress, socialize, or express themselves [10]. Applying Lebeda and Benedek’s framework to such creative activities seems complicated. What exactly triggers metacognitive engagement and allows people to sustain it in the absence of clear task-related cues? For example, while the outcome of task performance evaluation might indeed be the key reason to continue the process or abandon it, this decision is quite complicated in reality. If, as proposed, metacognitive monitoring forms the basis of task-oriented intention to act (*I will*), then it might not be that easy to distill it from a self-oriented judgment of capability (*I can*) or personal value the activity holds (*I care*). The degree to which people exercise *actual* control over their actions is steeped in their *perceived* control, which is how a person sees their dispositions and abilities in a given situation or task.

Thus, we suggest the current conceptualization of creative metacognition could (and should) be further dynamized. We see great potential in making the framework dynamic by emphasizing how core metacognitive components interact with the *perceived agency* [11] in the creative process. This integration could illuminate metacognitive phenomena that are hardly explainable when viewed through a purely “cold” lens. Imagine a situation where one chooses to disengage from a task despite positive (e.g., “the task goes smoothly for me”) and accurate performance assessment. This illustrates how the metacognitive mechanism of *control* (i.e., task disengagement) being informed by *monitoring* doesn’t function as proposed. Incorporating components of perceived agency—here, *creative centrality*, which would account for the possibility that a person may not care about creativity and sees no reason to express it in a given context—could help unpack such phenomena.

Lebuda and Benedek mention the agentic aspects of the creative process primarily to differentiate creative self-beliefs from “cold” knowledge about cognition. Whether such a clear distinction should be drawn within the “static” component of creative metacognition is not apparent [12]. We propose that integration is also needed for the “dynamic” metacognitive structures intertwined with dynamically conceptualized facets of creative agency, especially creative confidence and centrality. Indeed, there can be various reasons behind creative underperformance, from insufficient abilities and knowledge to ineffective metacognitive monitoring and control and the lack of perceived agency. One intriguing finding that could be better understood when looking at the *metacognition x agency* interaction is that while self-beliefs are generally positively linked to creative outcomes at the between-person level, being overly confident in one’s creative abilities might sometimes hinder performance at the within-person level [13]. Isn’t the explanation for this effect metacognitive? Perhaps believing in one’s capability to perform well makes a person less vigilant, leading to fewer resources being allocated to the metacognitive evaluation of one’s performance and subsequent regulation.

This is not to say the theory of creative metacognition should now be pursued as a grand theory of everything. Still, we might need even more diverse perspectives and nuanced views to understand better how people navigate creativity, from short divergent thinking problems to self-initiated little-c acts to complex and prolonged creative projects. Each step forward matters: Lebuda and Benedek have indeed placed an important brick in the wall. Yet, let us not forget of the broader structure we aim to build. To reinforce it before any isolated bricks begin to tumble, we still call for more integration.

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